

THE PROCESS OF ASSESSING NATIVE LANGUAGE LESSONS IN CREATIVE SCHOOLS BASED ON INTERNATIONAL REQUIREMENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18188302>

Abstrakt. *In this article, the organization provides information about the creation of the international company Cognia, Inc., this article covers the main areas of work and the accreditation process for educational institutions. A scientific analysis of the organization's activities and the results of research on this topic is provided. Using examples from creative schools, Cognia's accreditation process is explained.*

Keywords: *Cognia, AdvanceD and Measured Progress, accreditation, certification, K-12, professional development, Christian Schools (LCS), LCS model*

Introduction

Cognia is a leading global education organization providing accreditation, quality assessment, and continuous improvement services for schools and educational institutions. Cognia develops and implements strategies for improving educational effectiveness based on best practices and scientific research. It focuses on developing critical assessment and reflection skills in students and teachers, thereby improving the quality of teaching and learning. The organization's roots go back centuries: Cognia was formed in 2019 through the merger of "AdvancED," which had been in operation since 1895, and "Measured Progress," founded by Mark A. Elgart [1:1-3]. Cognia currently connects more than 40,000 educational institutions in over 100 countries, reaching approximately 17 million students. Cognia's core areas and services include:

- ✓ **Accreditation and certification:** Cognia provides certification and accreditation services for educational institutions;
- ✓ **Assessment and testing:** Works with midterm and final tests to assess students' performance;
- ✓ **Professional development:** Focused on teachers, it has an online platform called Cognia Learning Community where teachers and school administrators can continuously improve their skills;
- ✓ **Empowering and improving schools:** Develops and helps implement programs for continuous improvement of schools and educational systems;
- ✓ **Accreditation process:** Accreditation typically involves a school's self-assessment and an on-site review. Accreditation periods typically range from six months to several years;
- ✓ **New directions and expansion:** In 2024, Cognia expanded its educational assessment services offerings through the acquisition of CenterPoint Education Solutions. This enabled the organization to provide assessment capabilities across the K-12 system (from elementary school to high school);

- ✓ **Network cooperation:** Cognia provides teachers and educational leaders with an online platform for sharing experiences, discussing current issues, and improving their skills. This platform allows teachers to analyze their colleagues' lessons, and allows supervisors to evaluate teaching quality. Furthermore, teachers have the opportunity to work on their own development and improve their skills using this platform.

Literature review and methodology

The international scientific community has conducted research on the impact of Cognia accreditation on the functioning and development of educational institutions. В частности, изучались мнения учителей и руководителей школ об аккредитации Cognia. Specifically, the survey examined teachers' and school leaders' opinions on Cognia accreditation. The study included teachers and school leaders in countries accredited by Cognia. The research focused on assessing the importance of accreditation for school development and analyzing the thinking levels of K-12 students, subject area coordinators and school principals. The results showed that school principals generally gave the most positive assessment of Cognia accreditation. More than half of the teachers also rated accreditation positively, emphasizing its contribution to improving the quality of education. However, some teachers noted that the strict requirements and standards set within accreditation may lead to excessive standardization, potentially limiting student creativity and autonomy [2:1-14].

Table 2. Educators' Perceptions Pertaining to Accreditation.

Items	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Mean (SD)
Management of school facilities					
Accreditation procedures ensure school facilities and infrastructure are in good conditions.	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	366 (86.5%)	57 (13.5%)	3.13 (0.34)
Accreditation procedures impact positively on the management of communication channels amongst faculty.	99 (23.4%)	240 (56.7%)	53 (12.5%)	31 (7.3%)	2.04 (0.81)
Accreditation procedures ensure that the provision of safety is adequate at school.	0 (0.0%)	7 (1.7%)	275 (65.0%)	141 (33.3%)	3.32 (0.50)
Accreditation procedures support an adequate learning technologies infrastructure at school.	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	273 (64.5%)	150 (35.5%)	3.35 (0.48)
Accreditation procedures support an adequate resource allocation at school.	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	291 (68.8%)	132 (31.2%)	3.31 (0.46)
Accreditation procedures support better management operations at school.	13 (3.1%)	220 (52.0%)	171 (40.4%)	19 (4.5%)	2.46 (0.63)
Accreditation procedures support better learning environment for students.	0 (0.0%)	113 (26.7%)	271 (64.1%)	39 (9.2%)	2.83 (0.57)
Accreditation procedures support better working environment for faculty and staff.	72 (17.0%)	225 (53.2%)	107 (25.3%)	19 (4.5%)	2.17 (0.76)

The effectiveness of Cognia's accreditation activities has been the subject of a number of research studies that have examined the role of accreditation in improving the quality of education in schools using quantitative methods, with a focus on the Cognia Continuous Improvement model. One study examining the impact of the Burroughs League of Christian Schools (LCS) accreditation process on schools aimed to examine the impact of improving leadership capacity and introducing new instructional capacity into the educational environment on school effectiveness. Burroughs used a quantitative method to identify problem areas in K-12 schools by surveying 25 school principals. The results of the study showed that school leaders highly value accreditation, noting its significant impact on school effectiveness ($d = 2.38$). This result was higher than expected. Eighty percent of teachers participating in the survey also reported improved effectiveness. The researcher concluded that accreditation is a dynamic

process that contributes to significant improvements in school performance. Leaders noted that management skills increased by an average of 4.22% after accreditation [3:4-18].

A study by L. Davis looked at issues of school effectiveness and equity through Cognia accreditation, as well as issues of quality education in schools with multilingual students [4:3-9].

Dr. Mark A. Elgart, PhD, developed a multi-year plan to achieve effectiveness, and educational institutions in many countries around the world are currently working and being accredited under this project [5:4].

In recent years, research has examined how Cognia accreditation and the national supervision system complement each other and what role they play in improving the quality of education [6].

Results and discussion

A cooperation agreement was signed between the Agency for Specialized Educational Institutions under the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the international organization Cognia, Inc., under which creative schools in Uzbekistan became among the first, Cognia-accredited schools. The goal of this agreement is to elevate these schools to a new level of excellence, in line with international educational standards.

The Cognia international accreditation process involves preliminary familiarization of educational institutions with the requirements imposed, the management principles in accordance with these requirements, international standards for assessing the quality of education, and advanced teaching methods. Over the course of several years, these elements have been gradually introduced into the educational system. After completing the adaptation and monitoring period, the school undergoes the accreditation process and receives the corresponding certificate. Thus, creative schools in Uzbekistan are included among the educational institutions of the K-12 category that meet internationally recognized quality standards.

How does Cognia begin its work?

First and foremost, it connects school administration and teachers to its platform. A high level of English proficiency when using the platform facilitates productive work. On this platform, teachers can analyze each other's English lessons, conduct research, surveys, and improve their skills accordingly. This, firstly, establishes discipline and consistency in work, prevents red tape in a modern technologically advanced society, and also fosters accuracy and fairness in the evaluation of colleagues, creating a mutual exchange of experience.

In preparation for Cognia accreditation, a series of seminars was held, including theoretical and practical sessions on the assessment criteria used by Cognia. This resulted in assistance in preparing the materials necessary for initial accreditation.

Cognia accreditation involves assessing the performance of school administration and teachers based on 31 standards. These standards include requirements for the culture of the educational environment, in particular, the respectful attitude of the leader towards the teacher and student, mutual support, the organization of effective document flow, cooperation in achieving educational goals, the establishment of effective communications, etc.

A detailed study of student assessment procedures allows for tangible progress in improving their knowledge. At the beginning of the school year, diagnostic testing is administered in various subjects to determine students' initial knowledge levels. Throughout the quarter, an action plan aimed at improving these indicators is developed and implemented. Key conclusions on the effectiveness of the measures taken are drawn at the end of the quarter. The overall performance of students at the end of the quarter is presented as a percentage in the form of diagrams and tables, and a statistical report is generated.

Percentage indicators are presented in text form. Based on the data obtained, the performance level of each student in the class is determined and a work plan is developed for students experiencing difficulties in mastering the material.

№	Grade	Student experiencing difficulties in mastering knowledge (full name)	Subject	Topics that are difficult to grasp or have gaps	Subject teacher (full name)	Due date
1	8-A grade	Usakova Guljamila	Karakalpak language	Working on problematic issues. Structure of the complement. Structure of the attribute. Logical stress. Homonyms. Complex verbs. Structure of the complement. Reflections on national culture.	Z.Kazimbetova	13, 25 January

Based on the data obtained, the academic performance of each student in the class is determined and an individualized student work plan is developed. Furthermore, these same data are used to identify students with high academic performance. The goal is to improve student assessment scores in each subsequent quarter.

Conclusion

The results of the international organization Cogna demonstrate the formation of a close connection with students that goes beyond simply monitoring their academic performance. Cogna promotes student engagement in social life, fosters relationships with others, creates a

healthy learning environment, and encourages competition between teachers, students, and educational leaders. The organization not only works to improve the quality of education but also promotes respect for the culture, customs, and traditions of other peoples among the younger generation.

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